

Reconstruction of background radiation emissivity of urban structures using a truck-based detector array

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Abstract—Modeling and optimizing radiological threat detection problems in urban areas is facilitated through prior characterization of background activity distributions. The background emissivity of static objects such as buildings and roads is highly dependent on the composition of these elements of urban scenes. We perform a feasibility study to determine whether truck-based (non-imaging) detector measurements can be used to estimate the relative contributions of potassium-40, uranium and thorium (KUT) to the background emissions of surfaces. To do this, we simulate a simple urban scene, and assign realistic KUT compositions to structures. The detectors on the truck are completely characterized in terms of spectral response vs. angle of incidence using Monte Carlo simulation of all three background components, with each component being expressed as a spectral basis function. The truck moves along a trajectory through this environment and measures the background activity. Assuming knowledge of the position of surfaces (as would be determined using 3D maps or optical survey data), we estimate the KUT composition. We show that the inverse problem is sufficiently well-conditioned to solve for the K-40 component, but not for reconstructing the much smaller relative activities due to U and Th.

I. INTRODUCTION:

Systems for radiological threat detection cannot be simultaneously optimized for maximum probability of detection and minimum false alarm rate without knowledge of what constitutes the natural background activity in a particular environment [1]. Urban areas can be surveyed using mobile detectors in order to obtain a characterization of the background. The value of such surveys is improved if the measured activity can be attributed to known structures. This is because the inverse problem of solving for the strength and location of a threat source will be better conditioned if the corresponding information regarding background sources is known. We can also limit the possible solutions by imposing more constraints, such as confining sources to within building outlines.

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Inferring (reconstructing) the contributions of individual structures in an urban environment to the aggregate measured background activity is a challenging inverse problem. Our aim is to determine whether useful solutions can be found in even the most simple of scenarios. To do this requires: a simple scene, a realistic detector model, and a trajectory of the detector through the environment that is typical in terms of complexity and duration.

II. METHODS:

As detector system, we employ the Radiation Mobile Analysis Platform (RadMAP), which is a truck that contains 100 NaI and 24 HPGe detectors [1]. While the NaI detectors may be used in imaging mode in conjunction with a coded-aperture mask, we do not use the mask for imaging in this work. (Coded-aperture imaging is not effective for extended sources.) The detectors are characterized in terms of angular-spectral response by Monte Carlo simulation. Angular sampling is performed over a 2,880 vertex tessellated sphere, which realizes an angular resolution of approximately 3° . The simulated characterization sources are placed in the far field for lines of incidence (LOI) that do not intersect the ground plane beneath the wheels of the truck. The LOI are lines joining a centroid on a face of the tessellated sphere to the origin of the detector system, which we define as the center of the NaI array). The remaining sources are placed at the intersection of these lines with this ground plane. We perform 3 simulations per source position, one for each of the KUT component basis spectra, which appear in the upper panel of Figure 1. As an example of a detector characterization, the lower panel of Figure 1 plots the response of the HPGe detectors to the ^{40}K spectrum at 1461 keV. Calculation of the full set of responses is highly computationally intensive, since 2880×3 simulations are required.

The simple scene is shown in Figure 2. Surfaces are assigned realistic KUT values for the materials: granite (building), sandstone (building), wood (building), limestone concrete (building), cement (road) [2]. The truck trajectory also appears in this figure. Figure 3 illustrates, as example, the Th background activity we assigned to the structures.

Background activity was scaled to match the mean recorded count rates obtained by the HPGe detectors when RadMAP was driven through the central urban district of Oakland, CA. This amounted to approximately 12,000 and 600 counts per second in the NaI and HPGe arrays, respectively.

Fig. 1. *Upper*: Normalized spectral basis functions used to express background activity. The basis functions shown here apply to the HPGe detector. *Lower*: Detector response versus angle to the ^{40}K basis function of the HPGe detectors, for the energy bin containing the 1461 keV photopeak.

Fig. 2. The simulated simple scene consists of four building surfaces and a road surface. The blue line shows the trajectory of the truck through the scene.

Our forward measurement model is described as:

$$p_j^{bl} = \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{i=1}^I \int_{T^l} \int_{E_b} \frac{s_i^m(E) w_{\mathbf{k}^{ij}}^m(E) \tau_{\mathbf{k}^{ij}}(E)}{\|\mathbf{x}_i(t) - \mathbf{x}_j(t)\|^2} dE dt + W, \quad (1)$$

where p_j^{bl} is the measurement recorded in energy bin b during measurement period l of duration T^l . A particle is incident along direction vector \mathbf{k}^{ij} .

Emission from each surface is modeled using a mesh. The counts recorded for all measurements are due to a total of I of these discrete elements. A source generates events from M spectral basis functions, at rates proportional to the s_i^m . (We use 3 basis functions in our KUT analysis.) The detector response to incident radiation along direction

Fig. 3. This image shows the scene with the Th activity of each surface indicated.

\mathbf{k}^{ij} , for component spectrum m at energy E is $w_{\mathbf{k}^{ij}}^m(E)$. The transmission factor between source and detector, which incorporates attenuation due to air and known intervening structures, is given by $\tau_{\mathbf{k}}^{ij}$. The trajectories of the source and detector elements are denoted as $\mathbf{x}_i(t)$ and $\mathbf{x}_j(t)$, respectively.

Equation 1 can be cast as a matrix equation, with all of the factors that weight the s_i^m absorbed within a matrix \mathbf{F} that transforms \mathbf{s} (containing the s_i^m) into the measurement vector:

$$\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{s}.$$

This can be inverted using a weighted non-negative least squares to yield estimates of the KUT components for each source:

$$\hat{\mathbf{s}} = \arg \min_{s_i^m \geq 0, \forall i, m} (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{F} \mathbf{s})^T \mathbf{W} (\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{F} \mathbf{s}). \quad (2)$$

III. EVALUATION

We perform 1,000 reconstructions using different Poisson-noise realizations of the background activity.

IV. RESULTS

We find that the ^{40}K components exhibit low bias and variance. However, because their relative contributions to total background activity are much smaller (at least with the materials simulated), the variance of the U and Th coefficients is high.

V. DISCUSSION

We have used a highly simplified scenario to investigate the potential feasibility of reconstructing the individual components of the background radiation produced by urban structures. We employed realistic detector models and background count rates. Our results show clear potential for accurately recovering the ^{40}K contributions, since this isotope is the strongest source in most building materials. In cases where U and Th contributions dominate, these should also be well-recovered.

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